

MULTI LIVE-FEED MOULDING FOR AVOIDANCE OF MICROPOROSITY AND FOR THE
PRODUCTION OF SPECIFIED FIBRE ORIENTATION AND DISTRIBUTIONS IN FIBRE
REINFORCED MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Conventional injection moulding technique supplies a molten moulding material to a cavity, through an entrance which may subsequently be divided into a number of runners, to various gating points within the cavity. The pressure to all these gating points is, however, supplied by the single feed point. In multi live-feed moulding (MLFM) a single feed is split into a plurality of feeds in which each one is capable of supplying pressure to the cavity - independently of the others. The mould cavity may then be considered to be a cell which, by the action of live feed devices, provides for specified shear, pressure and temperature profiles on the solidifying melt - thereby providing for optimum control of fibre orientation in complex shaped parts.

MLFM applies to any mouldable material, including thermoplastic and thermosetting plastics matrix composites, and for metal and ceramic matrix composites converted into complex shapes with the aid of polymer binders.

INTRODUCTION

Processes for the production of specified orientations of reinforcing fibres, to give optimum physical properties in finished components, include filament winding, pultrusion and the use of pre-pregs for insert moulding or squeeze casting. The principal subject of this paper is a new technique for modifying the internal structure of fibre reinforced mouldings. In principle, the process [1, 2] applies to any mouldable material which includes - in addition to fibre reinforced plastics - ceramic and metal matrix composites, formulated to contain a polymer binder. The process, which uses oscillating packing pressures at a multiplicity of feed points

to the mould cavity, gives mouldings that are free of microporosity, even in products of large cross-section. Discontinuities in properties normally associated with internal weld lines are also much reduced. More importantly, enhanced and controlled alignment of fibres can be achieved in reinforced materials. Preferred alignment of fibres can be produced by design in parts of complex shape using a single process.

One of the main functions of the process is for the single feed from the injection moulder to be split into a plurality of feeds in which each one is capable of supplying pressure to the cavity independently of the others. As a consequence of this feature, the new process has been named 'Multiple Live-feed Moulding' (MLFM).

THE MULTI LIVE-FEED PROCESS

The Brunel technology involves an auxiliary packing device fitted between the mould cavity and the nozzle of the injection machine. It has hydraulically activated pistons located in the feed channels to the gates of the mould - the frequency and amplitudes of the pistons' movements during the fill and hold stages of the injection cycle being controlled by electronic pressure valves via a microprocessor. Unlike a conventional multi-gate single feed, the new technique allows the pressures at each feed point to be varied independently of the others. As a result, the material in the gates can be kept alive whilst the mould is filled and packed, and the solidifying melt can, itself, be subjected both to shear forces and to oscillating packing pressures, as well as static packing pressures.

The operation of the device may be understood by considering the twin-gated system shown in Figure 1. The figure consists of three parts: The injection moulder barrel A, the two live-feed packing head B, and the mould C. In addition, there is an auxiliary hydraulic power unit. The pistons are, initially, set to allow the mould to be filled through one channel or two channels. By activating the pistons (P) at the same frequency, but with a phase difference of 180C, the melt can be sheared within the cavity whilst it is solidifying. The main effects of this mode of operation is to align any reinforcing fibres at the melt-solid interface and, in some cases, to influence molecular orientation.

If the pistons are driven at the same frequency and in phase, the melt is compressed and decompressed at the set frequency. Finally, the pistons

can be used to apply static pressure to the cavity through the gates. The moulding operation can be controlled by a predetermined packing programme to ensure that the service requirements of the products are met in the most efficient and economic way.

The experimental results summarised below were gained with a two live-feed device fitted to a Daniels 350-120 injection moulder. The use of a microprocessor control allows up to 20 separate stages of mould packing. For each of these stages, any of the three options referred to above, can be used. In addition, the stage duration, packing pressures, frequency and background pressure (the pressure from the injection moulder barrel which feeds the device) can all be reset for the different packing stages.

APPLICATION OF THE MULTI LIVE-FEED PROCESS

The multi live-feed process has been applied with advantage to a wide range of thermoplastics including polyolefins, polyamides, PEI, PES and PEEK with and without reinforcing fibres, as well as self-reinforcing liquid crystal polymers. It has also been used with thermosetting dough moulding compounds. Applications include:

- (a) The elimination of microvoids and microcracks in thick-sectioned fibre reinforced mouldings at substantially lower packing pressures than required when an oscillating packing pressure is used [3, 4].
- (b) The enhancement of internal weld line strength by reorientation of fibres at internal weld line interfaces after mould filling.
- (c) The enhancement of tensile modulus and strength by the progressive alignment of fibres at the melt-solid interface during solidification.

Results supporting the claims (a), (b) and (c) have been gained from mouldings ranging from 3 to 20 mm thick. Representative results based on glass fibre reinforced polypropylene and nylon 6.6 are presented below. Mechanical test data is supported by X-ray microradiography which provides clear evidence for reorientation of fibres following the activation of multi live-feeds, including conclusive evidence for the almost complete alignment of fibres through the thickness of 20 mm thick mouldings.

The results are typical, in that they represent the scale of the enhancement possible with multi live-feed moulding in fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites, as well as heavily filled polyester thermosets containing typically by weight 59 per cent spherical filler, 15 per cent fibres and 17 per cent polymer. This composition is similar to those of

matrix, fibre and binder applying in metal or ceramic matrix composites processed with the aid of a polymer binder.

RESULTS

Tensile Modulus Enhancement of 30% GFR Polypropylene.

Two series of 20 x 20 mm cross-section mouldings were produced using a gating system similar to that illustrated in Figure 1. Production of mouldings free from gross internal voiding was not possible by conventional static hold pressure injection moulding. Elimination of internal voids was achieved by the use of an oscillating hold pressure [3], following initial mould filling, achieved by synchronising the operation of the two packing pistons - Series I.

The second series of mouldings - Series II - was packed using two live-feeds programmed to operate at 180° out of phase for short periods in between longer periods in which the pistons were operated in phase to pack the moulding. The balance of in phase and out of phase operation selected to gain optimum fibre alignment for the shortest moulding cycle.

Samples were cut from the two series of mouldings to measure through the thickness variations in tensile modulus. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Change in tensile modulus with depth in 30% GFR polypropylene.

Depth (mm)	2.0	6.0	10.0	14.0	18.0
Modulus (GPa) - Series I	3.9	6.1	1.7	5.5	3.4
Modulus (GPa) - Series II	4.3	7.7	7.7	7.0	5.6

These results show that the modulus of the bar made, using the multi live-feed process, is significantly higher than the mouldings made with symmetric mould packing. A four-fold increase in modulus applies at the centre of the Series II mouldings compared with Series I. The average modulus of the whole 20 mm thick injection moulded bar is approximately equal to the manufacturer's data for this material, which is usually based on 3 mm thick mouldings.

The enhanced modulus is attributed to a greater degree of fibre alignment along the length of Series II mouldings compared to Series I.

This is clearly borne out by contact X-ray radiography - as illustrated in Figure 2 - which shows the preferred fibre orientation at the centre of the 20 mm thick mouldings. The arrow is parallel to the process direction joining the two gates, G1 and G2, to the mould cavity in Figure 1.

Enhancement of Internal Weld Line Strength in 30% GFR Nylon 6.6

Prior to injection moulding, the long glass fibre reinforced nylon - ICI Verton AG1030 - was dried in vacuum for 12 hours at 100 C. The barrel and mould temperature were set at 280 C and 10 C, respectively.

Two sets of 6 mm thick bars containing internal weld lines were moulded. One set was prepared using a static packing pressure. In the second set, the two live-feeds were activated asymmetrically two or three times, immediately following initial mould filling, and followed by a static packing pressure. The small number of oscillations were used to gain preferred fibre orientation without severe fibre attrition.

The mean of five measurements of the tensile strength of mouldings, conditioned at atmospheric conditions for one month in each case, were:

	<u>Without live-feed</u>	<u>With live feed</u>
Internal weld line strength	52.4MPa	158MPa

The action of the two live-feeds was to cause re-alignment of fibres in the vicinity of the internal weld lines, thereby causing a threefold increase in weld strength. The X-ray microradiographs in Figure 3 show a very pronounced preferred glass fibre orientation parallel to the injection direction when two live-feeds are used, compared with a predominantly transverse fibre orientation at the interface in the conventionally produced weld lines.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In multi live-feed moulding, the mould cavity can be considered to be a cell which, by the action of live-feeds, provides for specified shear and pressure profiles on the solidifying melt. This leads to the formation of specific fibre orientation distributions at the melt-solid interface as it progresses from the outer surface to the core of a moulding during solidification. Mechanical property enhancement associated with the development of preferred fibre orientation in thick-sectioned thermoplastic matrix composites is illustrated above. The MLFM process provides a route for increasing control over - and the optimisation of - a wide range of physical properties in complex shaped parts.

The process simultaneously provides for efficient packing of the mould cavity, thereby eliminating microcracks and microvoids, the elimination of internal weld line defects in the core, as well as enhancement of preferred fibre orientation. Selection of the pressure and frequency profile will take into account the requirement not to prolong cycle time unnecessarily, and to keep fibre degradation to a minimum.

Multi live-feed moulding applies to heavily filled polymers, including dough moulding thermosets [5], thereby providing a route for the moulding of metal and ceramic matrix composites materials, processed with the aid of polymer binders, and giving - prior to binder removal and sintering - [6]-mouldings free from microcracks and microvoids and preferred orientation of fibres.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge financial support from the British Technology Group.

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Figure 1. Schematic diagram of an arrangement for a two live-feed moulding process.

Figure 2. X-ray microradiographs showing the orientations of glass fibres at the centres of mouldings produced conventionally (a) and with two live-feeds (b).

a

← I D →

b

← I D →

Figure 3. X-ray microradiographs taken through internal weld lines in 30% long glass reinforced nylon, produced by (a) conventional injection moulding, (b) two live-feed moulding. The process direction is represented by I.D.